

BUILDING THE DATA-DRIVEN ARCHIVE: AN ASYNCHRONOUS, INTEROPERABLE, EVENT-DRIVEN, LOW-CODE DATA WONDERLAND

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Abstract – This poster describes work-in-progress and lessons learned in our move towards a robust, flexible, modern data infrastructure for the digital archive. We have implemented data transformation capability via a low-code commercial ETL tool, and service integration via an asynchronous messaging architecture. This provides powerful but ‘light touch’ interoperability across systems with different maturity, governance, technical architecture and data models. Our next iteration will introduce a centralized, machine-readable data catalogue to enable data-driven processing. The long-term vision is of a full data ecosystem (data mesh/data fabric).

This approach is highly compatible with archival concerns (intellectual control, integrity, provenance). We find that engaging with data-centric practices has brought greater consistency, efficiency and a fresh perspective on our work as a digital archive.

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I. INTRODUCTION – A DATA-CENTRIC ARCHIVE

The UK National Archives (TNA) has been a working digital archive for c20 years. Our legacy technology prevents scaling up to handle more frequent, larger volume transfers: our systems are not readily interoperable and our process includes manual steps. We are starting to recognise that practical digital archiving is, fundamentally, a data-centric undertaking and have embarked on a transformation to embrace a more data-driven approach.

II. PROBLEM – MANUAL WORK & LOW GOVERNANCE

Our digital archivists carry out a huge volume of work to prepare data for ingest into our systems. They use Excel, Python, XLSX and even legacy PERL. This has been our accepted way of working but will not scale as transfer volumes grow.

Manual work also brings risks: it is difficult to document and audit; scripts are continuously tweaked and may not be thoroughly tested; scripts have low re-usability, are inefficient to create and run and hard to share. More significantly, the scripts encapsulate business rules which may not be documented elsewhere. We have no mechanism for ensuring rules are consistently expressed or for checking whether changes to rules have been reflected.

III. PROPOSAL – A MODERN DATA ECOSYSTEM

Our vision is to apply data-centric approaches [1] to automate processing, reduce risks and realise opportunities. Core components include: data transformation; event infrastructure; data catalogue; and data governance. Our preferred delivery model is to look to the market for mature, supported tooling and build only where we can add value.

IV. STEP 1: DATA TRANSFORM / ETL

Data operations span analysis, assessment, cleansing; formatting, aggregation; and loading data. Many tools focus on databases but we also need to

work with unstructured documents. We selected Talend [2] as our preferred tool.

We started with a common, local, toolset to let archivists assemble pipelines quickly, configuring via a GUI, not scripting or coding. The next iteration deployed the tool as a service to support logging, versioning, component re-use and automation.

Common tooling removes the need for local data transformation code, allowing services to focus on core needs. Centralization provides visibility and supports audit (and provenance) when deployed in conjunction with a data catalogue and governance.

V. STEP 2: EVENT-DRIVEN INFRASTRUCTURE

In our event-driven architecture, services listen to a message queue to hear about completed actions. If a service hears that a data package is available, it can act on this when ready and then send a message in turn. This makes each activity or transform a discrete entity that is autonomous and non-linear in execution, and orchestrated by the queue.

The messaging infrastructure minimizes constraints and dependencies, letting us integrate systems with different data models. It enables each service to focus on its own priorities while fully contributing to our overall digital records journey.

VI. NEXT STEP – DATA CATALOGUE

A data catalogue captures knowledge of data sources, their structure and content. It maps data interactions and flows and may link to transforms or validation rules. The important innovation is to create and hold the catalogue itself as actionable data driving the products and services which rely on it. This provides direct value, unlike documentation that rapidly goes out-of-date. Currently we hold some of this insight within individual services, but consistency is low and coverage is patchy. We are about to embark on creating a centralised resource.

VII. FUTURE – DATA GOVERNANCE

Data governance captures business knowledge and makes it usable by people and computers alike – similar to archival taxonomies, vocabularies or authority records. A data governance platform provides central access to rules and standards and may even enforce these. It provides visibility of data models and variation across sources. We aim to investigate this as a future iteration to bring together data-centric services into a ‘data mesh’ or ‘data fabric’ [3].

VIII. BENEFITS, LEARNING & CONCLUSION

Our direction of travel is towards greater automation and higher volumes. We have a successful first iteration of steps 1 & 2 above and now see records flow from transfer through access, enrichment & preservation in effortless minutes, not weeks or months of manual effort. The collection of messages created along the way will provide wider benefit – to power a dashboard in our next iteration.

The new architecture supports parallel ingest into multiple systems. It minimizes change to existing services, removes process bottlenecks, improves efficiency, and will reduce barriers to embracing digital first, thinking and practice for the digital archive.

This is a long-term and potentially disruptive undertaking. It will deliver incremental benefit as our practice matures. This poster advocates for data-centric approaches and shares progress and lessons learned on the journey so far.

REFERENCES

- [1] Oliveira, Marcelo Iury S & Lóscio, Bernadette Farias, 2018. What is a data ecosystem? In Proceedings of the 19th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research. ACM, New York, NY, USA, Article 74, 1–9. DOI 10.1145/3209281.3209335
- [2] Talend: a complete, scalable data management solution. www.talend.com/uk

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